

Hydrogen Bonding and the Dielectric Properties of Aniline, *p*-Toluidine and Dimethylaniline

D. D. Deshpande and K. G. Kadamba

The dielectric constants of pure aniline, *p*-toluidine and dimethylaniline have been measured as a function of temperature near their melting points. The dielectric constant, refractive index and density of these liquids have also been measured at temperatures from melting point to 60°. Dipole moment of these substances in liquid state have been calculated using Onsager and Jatkar equations. The Frohlich $B(T)$ function obtained from $\epsilon-T$ data and the Kirkwood's g factor suggest the antiparallel cluster formation of aniline and *p*-toluidine due to self-association. It has been concluded, that the self-association cannot be through NH...N bonding but due to packing of molecules by putting benzene ring of one molecule above the other.

The study of self-association of aniline through N-H...N hydrogen bonding has drawn the attention of many investigators in the field of infra-red spectra¹⁻⁴, n.m.r. spectra^{5,6} and thermodynamics^{7,8} of solutions. There is no unique agreement of different workers on the nature and extent of self-association of aniline. When the data on dielectric constant and dipole moment were examined, a wide variation is observed in the literature data⁹⁻¹⁸ and hence this work was undertaken to study the dielectric properties of aniline, *p*-toluidine and dimethylaniline using spectroscopically pure samples.

1. J. Gordy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 464; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 7.
2. J. H. Lady and K. B. Whetsel, *J. Physic. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 1001.
3. N. Fuson, M. L. Josien, R. L. Powell and E. Utterback, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **20**, 145.
4. L. J. Bellamy and R. L. Williams, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1957, **9**, 341.
5. I. Yamaguchi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1961, **34**, 1606.
6. B. D. N. Rao, P. Venkateswarlu, A. S. N. Murthy and C. N. R. Rao, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1962, **40**, 963.
7. K. Kehiaian and K. S. Kehiaian, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 838.
8. M. V. Pandya, Ph.D. Thesis, I.I.T., Bombay (1968).
9. L. G. Groves and S. Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1094; 1937, 1782.
10. C. J. F. Bottcher, *Physica*, 1939, **6**, 59.
11. A. V. Few and J. W. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 753.
12. Inga Fischer, *Nature*, 1950, **165**, 239.
13. R. J. B. Marsden and L. E. Sutton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 599.
14. S. Nagakura and H. Baba, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **74**, 5693.
15. Eric G. Cowley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, Part 3, 3557.
16. G. A. Barclay, R. J. W. Le Fevre and B. M. Smyth, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, **47**, 357.
17. A. L. McClellan, 'Tables of Experimental dipole moments', W. H. Freeman and Company (1963).
18. J. W. Smith and (Miss) S. M. Walshaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, Part III, 3217.

Theory : A number of theories giving equations correlating the dielectric constant of the liquids with the dipole moment are available^{19,20}. But only those of Onsager²¹, Kirkwood²² and Jatkar²³ have been used for the purpose of the present discussion.

Onsager equation : In the Onsager theory, the field acting on a molecule in a polarised dielectric is divided into two parts; the cavity field G , which is proportional to E , the external field, and the reaction field R , which is proportional to the total electric moment and depends on the instantaneous orientation of the molecules. With these assumptions, Onsager obtained the equation,

$$\frac{(e-n^2)(2\epsilon+n^2)}{\epsilon(n^2+2)^2} \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N\mu^2}{9kT} \quad \dots (1)$$

It should be emphasized that though Onsager has taken into account long range interaction, he has neglected the short range forces which nevertheless, are the most important in the liquid state.

Kirkwood equation : Since the short range forces cannot be ignored in liquids, and especially in associated liquids, Onsager equation gives reasonably good results only for some liquids and the calculated moment varies considerably over a range of temperature. Short range forces are to a great extent responsible for the orientation of molecules in crystal lattices, and they tend to produce such orientation in small crystal-like domains in liquids. Because of these short range forces, the orientation of a dipole (irrespective of the influence of an external field) is not random with respect to its immediate neighbour, and in the consideration of the instantaneous dipole at a given point this should be taken into account.

On this basis, Kirkwood modified Onsager equation by taking into account the interaction between the nearest neighbours. Thus, if μ is the magnitude of the permanent dipole moment, then the product of the average moment $\overrightarrow{\mu}$ of the molecule in the cavity and its moment $\overrightarrow{\mu}^*$ due to interactions of the neighbour will be given by

$$\overrightarrow{\mu}\overrightarrow{\mu}^* = \mu^2(1+z\overline{\cos \gamma}) \quad \dots (2)$$

where z is the co-ordination number and γ is the angle between the nearest dipole, $\overline{\cos \gamma}$ is the average of all such possible relative orientations of the dipole pairs. The difficulty of solving Kirkwood equation lies in obtaining correct value of $\overline{\cos \gamma}$, which are not possible to predict without a supposition of structure of the given liquid. Introducing a parameter g as

$$g = (1+z\overline{\cos \gamma})$$

19. C. P. Smyth, 'Dielectric behaviour and structure', Chapter I, McGraw-Hill (1955).
20. C. J. F. Bottcher, 'Theory of Electrical Polarisation', Ch. VI and VII, Elsevier Publishing Co., Houston (1952).
21. L. Onsager, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1486.
22. J. G. Kirkwood, *J. Chem., Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 911; *Ann. N. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, **40**, 315; *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1946, **42A**, 71.
23. S. K. K. Jatkar, *Nature*, 1944, **153**, 222; *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1946, **28A**, Part II.

the Kirkwood equation would be

$$\frac{(\epsilon - n^2)(2\epsilon + n^2)}{\epsilon(n^2 + 2)^2} \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N g \mu^2}{9kT} \quad \dots (3)$$

which if $g = 1$ (when no interaction with nearest neighbour) reduces to Onsager equation.

Kirkwood pointed out that the departure of g from unity is a measure of degree of hindered relative molecular orientation arising from short range intermolecular forces. 'Normal' liquids show the value of g as unity whereas 'abnormal' or associated liquids shows values which depart significantly from unity. Thus the value of g can be used for the discussion of short range forces which exist in molecules such as self-association in pure liquids. It is obvious that the Kirkwood's angular correlation parameter g would be a function of temperature and concentration.

Jatkar equation : Jatkar²³ proposed an extraordinarily simple relationship between the dielectric constant and dipole moment in 1943. Unlike Onsager and Kirkwood theory which treated the polar molecule as spherical, Jatkar theory treats the polar molecule as needle shaped and hence totally anisotropic as a result of which only parallel and antiparallel orientation is possible. By applying arbitrarily the principle of quantum mechanics, Jatkar obtained the orientation polarization₀ as

$$P_0 = (\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{3kT} \left(\frac{J+1}{J} \right)$$

Since $(2J+1)$ is the total possible number of settings we have $2J+1 = 2$. Hence the orientation polarization is

$$P_0 = (\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{kT} \quad \dots (4)$$

It was found empirically that Jatkar equation was to be modified in order to cover the entire range of dielectrics. Associated liquids and ferroelectric substances gave correct moment values with the use of equation

$$P_0 = (\epsilon - n^2) \frac{M}{d} = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{k(T - \theta)} \quad \dots (5)$$

where θ is a transition temperature at which the dipole freezes. Simple liquids generally obey the equation (4), but in some cases it is to be modified to $\mu^2/1.5 kT$ showing increased freedom of orientation ($2J+1 = 3$). It is thus possible to discuss the association in pure liquids and the freedom of orientation in term of the values of $(2J+1)$ given by Jatkar equation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dielectric constant measurement of liquids were carried out by resonance method because of its high accuracy and simple circuitry. The precision condenser used was of the type 722N, General Radio Company, Mass, U.S.A. with a range from 100 to 1150 $\mu\mu F$, reading accurate to $\pm 0.1 \mu\mu F$. The dielectric cell was a gold plated coaxial brass cylinder with

teflon spacers. The dielectric cell was kept inside an air tight sample holder whose temperature was maintained at the desired temperature by means of a thermostat. The calibration of the cell was carried out from 25 to 50° by using pure and freshly distilled benzene.

The density measurement was made by means of a Lipkin bicapillary pycnometer. The capillary had a uniform bore of 1 mm. The bulb capacity was 15 ml. Care has been taken to prevent the loss of liquid by evaporation. The density data are highly reproducible and precise. The accuracy is 1 part in 10⁵.

The measurement of refractive index was made by means of Rayleigh's interferometer. The liquid whose refractive index was to be noted was kept in a specially designed glass cell. The temperature of the cell was maintained by circulating the thermostated water. The refractive index of the liquid was obtained as a difference with respect to a known standard. Pure benzene was used as a standard here. The scale of the interferometer was calibrated using solutions of benzene+carbon tetrachloride and benzene+cyclohexane as accurate refractive index data of these systems are available. Using a cell of 1 cm. path length and 5 ml. capacity, the accuracy of the refractive index measurement was 1 in 10⁶.

All weighings were done on a semimicrochemical balance weighing accurately upto 0.1 mg. The solutions were weighed in a ground glass stoppered flask so that errors due to evaporation of solvent are minimised.

Aniline and dimethylaniline used was E-Merck proanalysed, but were kept on potassium hydroxide pettelets for a week and distilled twice over zinc dust at a reduced pressure. Only a freshly distilled sample was taken for the purpose of measurements.

p-toluidine was B.D.H. analar and was purified by repeated crystallizations and finally distilled under reduced pressure. During the process of distillation, the condenser and the receiving flask were maintained at 50° by circulating hot water. The physical constants of all the purified samples agree closely with the literature values^{24,25}.

DISCUSSION

Experimental results of dipole moment and the Kirkwood factor *g* are given at different temperatures for pure aniline, dimethylaniline and *p*-toluidine, in Table I. In the case of aniline and dimethylaniline, the moment increases with increase in temperature for both Onsager and Jatkar equations. Whereas, it decreases with increase in temperature in the case of *p*-toluidine. It is interesting, however, to note that the moment tends to shift towards gas values as the temperature is increased for all the three substances. Kirkwood angular correlation parameter *g* is slightly more than unity in the case of aniline and *p*-toluidine, whereas it is less than unity in dimethylaniline. The Kirkwood's parameter *g* increases with temperature only in the case of dimethylaniline. This suggests that association of dimethylaniline may be of parallel clusters $\rightarrow \rightarrow$. If aniline and *p*-toluidine are associated, it must probably be through antiparallel clusters $\rightarrow \leftarrow$. Hence, for these two liquids *g*

24. A. Weissberger, 'Organic Solvents', Interscience Publishers, New York (1955).

25. J. Timmermans, 'Physico-Chemical Constants of Pure Organic Compounds'. Elsevier Publishing Company (1950 and 1965).

decreases with temperature. Further, since g is very nearly the same as unity it clearly indicates that NH-N association is not as strong as OH-O association of alcohols. Jatkar's method also supports this view as the result calculated with $1 kT$ formula are fairly in agreement with the gas value though for associated liquids, Jatkar equation takes the form $\mu^2 F/k(T-\theta)$. These results thus do not indicate self-association of anilines like alcohols. The reasons then, that the dielectric properties are not affected by self-association in anilines are that :

(i) The association is not through NH...N hydrogen bonding. The appearance of an infra-red band at 3200 cm^{-1} was assumed by several previous workers^{1-7, 26} to be a bonded NH vibration. This view however, is to be categorically discarded, as the infra-red frequencies of anilines have been recently reassigned by a careful isotope substitution studies by Evans²⁸ and Tsuboi²⁹. According to these authors the band at 3200 cm^{-1} is not due to bonded NH vibration but due to a combination of overtone of NH bending with NH stretching to give a Fermi resonance.

(ii) The extent of association is also very important. In the case of anilines the entire liquid will not be existing in dimeric or polymeric form like that of water or alcohol, but there will be a large number of monomeric molecules present, and the equilibrium will be established between the monomeric and dimeric species as follows :

With increased temperature, obviously, the equilibrium will be shifted towards the monomeric form. More insight about this behaviour is obtained from the experimental $\epsilon-T$ curves.

$\epsilon-T$ curves for pure substances: In the figure 1 are given the graphs of dielectric constant against temperature for pure aniline, dimethylaniline and *p*-toluidine. A sharp increase in dielectric constant has been observed at a temperature corresponding to the melting point for all these substances. These results reveal that the order-disorder transition of the dipoles occur at the melting point and there is no transition point in the solid state for these substances. More insight can be obtained about the orientations of these dipoles, by plotting Frohlich's²⁷ $B(T)$ function against temperature.

$$B(T) \approx [\epsilon(T) - \epsilon(0)] \cdot \frac{2\epsilon(T) + \epsilon(0)}{3\epsilon(T)} T.$$

The graphs of $B(T)-T$ have been shown in figure 2. According to Frohlich, the increase of $B(T)$ with increase in temperature (positive slope) indicates an increasing tendency to

26. S. K. K. Jatkar, Jatkar and Mukhedkar, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 715.

27. H. Frohlich, 'Theory of Dielectrics', Oxford University Press (1950), Ch. IV, p. 136.

28. J. C. Evans, *Spectrochimica Acta*, 1960, **16**, 428.

29. M. Tsuboi, *Spectrochimica Acta*, 1960, **16**, 505.

antiparallel orientations. This behaviour is observed for the present substances in the solid state. This means, the increase of temperature which gives rise to disorder and freedom of movement of dipoles from their lattice sites, makes them to form clusters like I

and such clusters are in maximum number at melting point. Above the melting point the $B(T)$ function rapidly diminishes with increase of temperature (negative slope) as these clusters

are rapidly destroyed due to thermal motions of the dipoles. According to Fröhlich, the negative slope of $B(T)-T$ curves indicate an increasing tendency of parallel orientations as in II.

TABLE I

Substance	Temperature °C	μ_D		g
		Onsager	Jatkar 1 kT	
Aniline	-5.0	1.58	1.54	1.13
	0.0	1.50	1.47	1.01
	20.0	1.50	1.47	1.01
	30.0	1.51	1.47	1.02
	40.0	1.51	1.47	1.02
	50.0	1.53	1.48	1.05
Dimethylaniline	4.0	1.38	1.31	0.735
	15.0	1.37	1.30	0.723
	25.0	1.40	1.31	0.759
	30.0	1.40	1.31	0.758
	50.0	1.44	1.33	0.799
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	45.0	1.38	1.30	1.10
	50.0	1.36	1.28	1.07
	60.0	1.34	1.25	1.03

The dielectric behaviour does not support the self-association of anilines through NH...N bonding, but indicates a loose cluster formation of parallel and antiparallel dipoles as shown in the diagram. The nature of the self-association is a loose cluster with benzene rings situated one above the other. Further there will be an equilibrium between monomeric and associated form of these molecules in the pure liquid state; the monomeric form being in larger concentration.

Department of Chemistry,
Indian Institute of Technology,
Powai, Bombay-76.

Received April 13, 1970